

ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPING INSTRUMENTAL PERFORMANCE SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: The article aims to identify pedagogical methods, organizational approaches and mechanisms used in the process of teaching instrumental performance. The article focuses on the basic principles of teaching instrumental performance, the relationship between the teacher and the student, as well as methodological methods for developing performance techniques. It also analyzes the organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for the effective organization of the educational process in instrumental performance and the theoretical and practical aspects of their use. The results of this article are determined by their practical significance in music education and the development of performance skills of young performers.

Keywords: Instrumental performance, students, pedagogical mechanism, performance technique, performance skills, rubab instrument, performance opportunities, performance skills.

Today's modern society places high demands on the training of music teachers in all respects. The improvement of the education system in Uzbekistan, changes in the socio-economic and spiritual spheres require a fundamentally new approach to assessing the professional skills of a modern music teacher. This requires the need for highly qualified teachers in society to open up advanced opportunities for teaching music in secondary schools, to effectively use existing opportunities in music education and to expand the level of their practical application in order to effectively develop the pedagogical skills of music teachers[2]. In this regard, the skills of students in playing instruments are of particular importance.

Instrumental performance, as one of the main branches of music education, is important not only for the development of musical skills, but also for the formation of artistic and aesthetic taste. In particular, the development of instrumental performance skills in students is carried out through a unique pedagogical approach and organizational mechanisms.

Nowadays, the goal of music education is to develop not only musical knowledge in students, but also the ability to play musical instruments. For this purpose, it is necessary to develop pedagogical mechanisms and methodologies for

the formation of musical performance skills in students, and to effectively organize the educational process. The organizational and pedagogical mechanisms used in the process of developing musical performance skills in students direct students to become excellent musicians not only technically, but also artistically, aesthetically and creatively.

The main goal of developing organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for the development of musical performance skills in students is to systematically analyze pedagogical approaches, methodological methods and organizational activities implemented in the educational process.

This process plays an important role not only in the development of musical skills, but also in the formation of musical culture. It also allows developing organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for the development of musical performance skills in students, improving the music education system and training students as highly qualified personnel.

Humanization of education, as one of the principles that implement the goals of the higher pedagogical education system, requires the actualization of mechanisms for developing the skills of musical performance of students in the field of music education. In this case, the discipline of musical performance should be developed with the purposeful use of the capabilities of educational materials, integrated connections of relevant disciplines, the conduct of classes based on the requirements of the time and their continuity, and processes in the professional pedagogical direction. In the development of musical performance skills of students in the field of music education, it is advisable to create effective mechanisms that allow the correct organization of the pedagogical process, the correct assessment of the situation, the correct solution of pedagogical problems, the analysis and enrichment of professional activities, avoiding various conflicts. Such mechanisms determine the development of musical performance skills of students in the process of professional activity.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. In order to develop students' musical performance skills, professors and teachers of the higher pedagogical education department of music education are required to have sufficient pedagogical skills. The future music teachers they prepare "...must be responsible for the education and upbringing of the younger generation, and at the same time, be able to demonstrate pedagogical skills, and make a worthy contribution to the training of qualified personnel as mature teachers" [3, p. 7]. Students studying in the field of music education should not only have pedagogical skills in organizing and conducting music lessons in secondary schools during their future professional activities, but also have sufficient musical knowledge, in particular, musical performance skills, in terms of professional skills. This indicates that the music

teacher can easily solve the difficulties and pedagogical problems of his professional activity. "In their time, Abu Nasr Farabi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Sa'di Shirazi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abdullah Avloni and others described in their works valuable information about the teaching profession, its difficulties, as well as the qualities that should be reflected in the personality of the teacher. Consequently, a teacher who does not understand the essence of the pedagogical process and does not have deep respect for the child cannot have an idea that ensures the effectiveness of education and human development. A teacher with high pedagogical skills should be able to understand the child, have a humane attitude towards him, correctly assess any pedagogical situation, resolve possible conflicts in a timely manner, be always progressive in his activities, and be able to connect the noble ideas that he instills in the minds of students in the development of society and the pedagogical process with life. [3, p. 8]

The development of students' musical performance skills should be the main goal of enriching their minds, musical worldview, expanding their professional intellectual knowledge, and teaching students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. We know that a skilled musician cannot convey his pedagogy to the student by performing his musical work perfectly, that is, he cannot teach another student his performance skills. There are also such performers who, although they are not excellent at performing, can convey and teach the student pedagogically. It is precisely the preparation of future music teachers who have achieved competence in both of these areas for their professional activities as mature personnel that is the ultimate goal of today's music department in higher education institutions[5]. In this sense, by developing organizational and pedagogical mechanisms to develop students' musical skills, and through the teaching process based on such mechanisms, their pedagogical skills will develop along with the development of their musical skills.

Below we present the organizational and pedagogical mechanism for teaching instrumental performance.

The organizational and pedagogical mechanism for teaching instrumental performance is aimed at ensuring the effective, systematic organization of the educational process and the development of students' performing skills, as well as their pedagogical skills. This mechanism includes the following main elements in organizing the activities and interactions of all participants in the music education system, from professors and teachers to students:

1. Pedagogical development and methodology. The organizational and pedagogical mechanism of teaching instrumental music performance includes methodological approaches aimed at developing students' performance technique and musical thinking. This methodology is based on the principles of an

individualized approach, integration of understanding and performance. In an individualized approach, it is necessary to individually develop the performance technique and musical knowledge of each student, taking into account their artistic abilities, and organize special classes.

Integration of understanding and performance of theoretical knowledge: to fully explain musical works to students, learn to express their content, and develop their performance techniques.

2. Organizational aspects. The organizational mechanism for teaching instrumental music includes the organizational stages necessary for the effective organization of the educational process. - planning and systematization of lessons. In this case, the correct selection of musical works, planning of lessons and classes, and the comprehensive development of students' performance activities are emphasized; - teaching methods in classes. This includes conducting group and individualized classes, providing students with an individual approach to learning instrumental music, and strengthening their performance techniques; - the role and approach of the teacher. This includes the teacher's approach to students, methods of assistance and encouragement directed at them. The teacher should work to create a positive environment that encourages students to develop their abilities.

3. Practical exercises and test exams. Practical exercises and test exams are important in the process of teaching instrumental music performance. - in practical exercises, students are taught to perform in various genres of instrumental music. These exercises help develop performance techniques and expressive means; - in test exams and class concerts, students are organized into various class concerts and test exams to evaluate their performance. Through this process, students have the opportunity to test their musical skills and gain practical experience.

4. Achieving and developing artistry in instrumental performance. The development of artistic aesthetics and artistic imagination also plays an important role in the organizational and pedagogical mechanism of studying instrumental performance. In this regard, it is necessary to organize activities that help students develop artistic imagination and aesthetic taste in performing musical works. Through artistic analysis of the work and a creative approach, students are taught to analyze musical works and create their own unique performance styles [6]. This helps to increase their creative abilities.

5. Educational and methodological materials. Educational materials and resources play an important role in teaching instrumental music performance. Methodological guides for students to study and perform musical works, methodological materials that help teachers in teaching instrumental music. Audio and video resources, creating opportunities for students to hear and see various instrumental works, developing their performance technique.

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In conclusion, the organizational and pedagogical mechanism for studying the performance of musical instruments creates the necessary foundations for a more effective and systematic organization of the music education process. This mechanism is aimed at the correct application of pedagogical methods and organizational approaches in the development of students' performance skills, through which the educational process can be made maximally effective..

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